

RESONATING SEMIPOLAR SINGLE BOND. PART VIII. HYPERCONJUGATION, STRENGTH OF ACIDS AND CALCULATION OF DIPOLE MOMENTS

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An alternative mechanism of hyperconjugation is put forward on the basis of the theory of the resonating semipolar single bond which is similar to Baker and Nathan's assumption and different from wave mechanical ideas as advanced by Pauling, Wheland and Mulliken. Wave mechanical representation is criticised on the grounds: (i) it assumes free ions as contributing structures, (ii) neglects the nature of the links, and also (iii) neglects the nature of the activating group. Active methylene compounds are shown to constitute a serious objection to the correctness of the theory as applied to hyperconjugation.

The mechanism on the basis of the theory of the resonating semipolar single bond is used to explain the shortening of bond lengths, strength of acids and the calculation of dipole moments of halogenated methanes. Calculated results thus obtained are very close to the observed values, whereas earlier calculations gave far divergent results.

Baker and Nathan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1844) put forward the concept of hyperconjugation to explain the abnormal behaviour of certain series of alkyl substituted compounds. They suggest that the duplet of electrons forming the C-H bond of an alkyl group, which is attached to an unsaturated carbon atom, is less localised than that in a similar C-C bond; hence, electron release is permitted by

a mechanism which is essentially a type of tautomeric effect: $\text{H}-\overline{\text{CH}_2}-\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}}-\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}}$. Pauling and others (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 927; Wheland, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, 2, 474) treat it as due to resonance in which ions and radicals behave as contributory structures, while in another treatment (Mulliken, Ricki and Brown, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 41) it is supposed to result from the conjugation of unsaturated centres

with 'quasi multiple' bonds composed of a number of single bonds: $-\text{H}_3\equiv\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}}-\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}}-\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}}-$

There are a number of difficulties with the wave mechanical concepts. Absence of colour indicates that resonance should not be postulated in an extreme form; even by itself contribution by ions and radicals appears to be improbable. A further difficulty is that these concepts do not take into consideration the nature of the links. Thus H-C links should behave in the same way as C-C links. This is obviously against facts. Nor do they consider the nature of the activating group; whereas in point of fact, hyperconjugation is markedly dependent upon the attached group. Moreover, cases of hyperconjugation involving only single bonds are also known. Thus, methylchloroform and chloroform have a value of μ equal to 1.8 and 1.15 respectively. This is interpreted as a second order hyperconjugation (Hurdis and Smyth, *ibid.*, 1942, 64, 2829), but the influence observed is much too large to be a second order effect and casts serious doubt on wave mechanical interpretations so far advanced. The inadequacy of these interpretations is clearly

indicated by compounds containing active hydrogen. The hyperconjugational resonance possibilities are in the order : $\text{CH}_3 > \text{CH}_2 > \text{CH}$ and this also should be the order of ionisability. Actually just the reverse is the case. Another point to be noted is that the activating groups may be the same or different, but the influence will be the same. This clearly points to the conclusion that hyperconjugation is nothing more than the possibility of conjugation of single bonds with other groups under the strong polarising influence of those groups. The theory of the resonating semipolar single bond puts forward the mechanism for such a type of conjugation. Baker and Nathan (*loc. cit.*) have cautiously remarked that the duplet in C-H is less localised than C-C bonds. It may be said that the polarising influences can semipolarise single bonds depending upon the polarising intensity of the group. Thus, a hyperconjugated system may be represented in an extreme forms as —

$$\text{H}-\overline{\text{CH}_2}-\text{C}-\overset{+\frac{1}{2}}{\text{C}} \longrightarrow \text{H} \dots \overset{+\frac{1}{2}}{\text{C}} \text{CH}_2 \dots \overset{-\frac{1}{2}}{\text{C}}$$
 Actually mesomeric part of the semipolarisation of single bonds comes into play. We can on this basis easily determine the groups which will lead to semipolarisation of single bond by considering the properties of the compound HX. If HX can behave as an acid, the group X may be supposed to be capable of semipolarising the single bond between itself and hydrogen. Thus, the following groups may be supposed to be capable of semipolarising single bonds : -Cl, -Br, -I, -SH, -C≡C, -COOEt, -CN, -NO₂ etc. Weaker influences are : C=C, -OH, >CO etc.

Bond Lengths

C=C, C≡N show their semipolarising influence in reducing the C-C bond length by 0.08 Å in methylacetylene, dimethylacetylene, dimethyldiacetylene, diacetylene, cyanogen and methyl cyanide (Pauling and others, *loc. cit.*). We may represent the molecules with a semipolar single bond as an extreme form :

Besides, a number of other structures may be written for the molecules. The presence of these resonating structures would stabilise hydrogen, and hence the acidic nature will not be so marked as in acetylene. Semipolarisation of hydrogen bonds results in the double bond character of C-C bond, and hence the shortening observed. The weak polarising influence of C=C influences adjacent single bonds but little (Pauling and Brockway, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1223). In chlorine compounds the inductive effect is prominent at the expense of the semipolarising tendency. Still it will be present to a certain extent which should lead to the development of this effect. The hyperconjugation can be shown better by iodine compounds where inductive effect being small due to equal electronegativity of the two atoms, semipolarisation is much more important. Still the shortening of the bond should take place in methylchloroform where the increase in dipole moment over chloroform has been suggested to be due to hyperconjugation (Hurdis and Smyth, *loc. cit.*).

Strength of Acids

Though a large amount of work has been done on the dissociation constant of acids, and a large number of electronic influences postulated, still the problem is not fully settled yet. Jenkins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1448) has added one more postulate. He starts with the work of Sidwick (*ibid.*, 1937, 694) and of Lennard-Jones and Coulson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 35, 822) which show that there is a linear relationship between resonance energy and ' n ', where ' n ' is the number of canonical forms for the molecules. He strives to show that extremely simple relations exist between ' n ' or some function of ' n ' and dissociation constant and activation energies. To get the requisite number of canonical forms in the case of phenyl- and diphenylacetic acids he assumes the following structures of some canonical forms :—

He admits that 'no simple picture' of the interaction can be given. It appears that two resonating structures at the end of a molecule can lead to a further stabilisation without the molecule resonating as a whole. If it were so, the length of the bond will be without any influence. To account for the value of ' n ' required, the resonance forms may be introduced by employing the postulate of the resonating semipolar single bond :

Similarly to account for the strength of trichloroacetic acid he supposes the forms to be :

This representation will lead to the impression that C—C bond is very strong in trichloroacetic acid. In fact, carbon bonds are greatly weakened by the presence of chlorine substituents, e.g. CCl_3CHO is easily converted into CHCl_3 , and Cl_3CHO is still more readily converted into CHI_3 . These difficulties may be removed easily if we represent the electron transfer in this case also by the semipolarisation of single bonds. Inductive effect is not sufficient by itself to account for the strength

of trichloroacetic acid, as on that basis it should be as strong as monochloroacetic acid. Semipolarisation of single bonds in this case can be represented as :

This representation will indicate both the strength of the acid and the weakness of the C-C bond.

Dipole Moments

The large increase in dipole moment of methylchloroform as compared with chloroform was attributed by Maryott, Hobbs and Gross (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 659) to a transfer of charge from the methyl carbon atom to the adjacent carbon atom and the transfer in turn of some of this charge to the chlorine atom. This is essentially a hyperconjugation of the second order, which is assumed by wave mechanical representation to be present in CH_3-CH_3 . It was first discussed from this point of view by Hurdis and Smyth (*loc. cit.*). It is clear that hyperconjugation of the second order should not be so very important as is actually the case with this compound. On the present theory we can explain it as

In fact, the present ideas can be used to calculate the dipole moments of halogenated alkanes. CH_4 is non-polar and so it is obvious that H and CH_3 are balancing each other. This being so, the difference between the dipole moments of HCl ($\mu=1.03$) and CH_3Cl ($\mu=1.86$) cannot be easily understood unless we make the assumption that the presence of chlorine is influencing C-H bonds. The nature of this influence cannot be pictured on any other ground except that of the theory of the resonating semipolar single bond. Due to polarisation HCl has a dipole moment of 1.03. If no other factor interfered, CH_3Cl would also have a dipole moment of about the same value. But the polarising nature of chlorine enables carbon to polarise attached C-H bonds to a certain extent. As actual semipolarisation has not taken place (absence of colour etc.) only the mesomeric part will be available. As semipolarisation means the total removal of electrons from molecular to the atomic orbital of one of the atoms, it will be treated as a scalar quantity. On this basis $\mu_{\text{CH}_3\text{Cl}} - \mu_{\text{HCl}}$ or 0.83D is the scalar sum of the semipolarisation brought about under the influence of Cl. The contribution of each of the hydrogen

atoms may therefore be placed at 0.83/3 or 0.28. As chlorine can accommodate one full electron, this amount of semipolarisation may be taken as the maximum mesomeric influence under the joint inductive and semipolarising effect of chlorine. If the inductive effect is less, as in Br and I compounds, the contribution due to semipolarisation will be greater, e. g. $\mu\text{CH}_3\text{Br} - \mu\text{HBr} = 1.80 - 0.78 = 1.02D$, $\mu\text{CH}_3\text{I} - \mu\text{HI} = 1.66 - 0.38 = 1.28D$. Calculating on this basis and adding the moments vectorially we have the following table indicating the actual dipole moments of the halogenated methanes and the values calculated on the basis of present ideas and the values calculated on the basis of mere vector addition with 1.86D as the values C-Cl dipole. It will be noticed that the results agree closely with the observed values (Table I).

TABLE I

Dipole moment of halogenated methanes.

Compounds.	Calculated.	Actual.	Calculated (older).
CH_3Cl	...	1.86	...
CH_2Cl_2	1.58	1.58	2.14
CHCl_3	1.12	1.15	1.86
CH_2Br	...	1.80	...
CH_2Br_2	1.35	1.39	2.07
CHBr_3	0.90	0.99	1.80
CH_3I	...	1.66	...
CH_2I_2	1.01	1.10	1.91
CHI_3	0.52	0.91	1.66

The only divergent value is in the case of iodoform. This is an exception that proves the rule as only iodoform of the above compounds is deeply coloured. This indicates that actual resonance has started. A similar phenomenon is met with in the case of *p*-nitroaniline where the increase in the dipole moment above the sum of the substituents is accompanied by the appearance of a deep colour.

Some other results for other types of chlorine derivatives of hydrocarbons are given in the table below. The results have been calculated by assuming that the hyperconjugational effect, the conferring as it does some double character, must be compounded vectorially in compounds such as

TABLE II

Substance.	Calc.	Obs.	Substance.	Calc.	Obs.
C_7H_5Cl	2.02	2.06	$CH_2 : CHCH_2Cl$	2.02	2.01
CH_3CHCl_2	2.03	2.07	<i>cis</i> - $CHCl : CHCl$	2.02	1.89
CH_3CCl_3 (app.)	1.86	1.79	C_6H_5Cl	...	1.52
$CH_3CH_2CH_2Cl$	2.02	2.04	<i>o</i> - $C_6H_4Cl_2$	2.13	2.25
$(CH_3)_2CHCl$	2.20	2.18	<i>m</i> - $C_6H_4Cl_2$	1.46	1.48
$CH_3CH : CHCl$	1.67	1.66	<i>p</i> - $C_6H_4Cl_2$	0.00	0.00

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